

Environmental analysis of factors affecting the development of sports entrepreneurship

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Abstract

The purpose of the present research was Environmental analysis of factors affecting the development of sports entrepreneurship. The statistical population included all professors, experts and sport entrepreneurs in Hamedan province. 30 people of them were selected to form the matrix of the paired index with index (component with component) using hierarchical analysis (AHP) analysis, by purposive sampling. The results of present study showed that the socio-cultural factors (0.555), economic factors (0.231), Political-legal factors (0.169) and environmental factor (0.045) had an effective role in development of sports entrepreneurship in Hamadan province. Also, among the socio-cultural factors, entrepreneurship education in schools and universities and Training of sports entrepreneurs in the province had an effective role. Considering the effective role of socio-cultural factors in the development of sports entrepreneurship in Hamadan province, it is necessary to take the necessary actions to change the attitude and view of individuals toward entrepreneurship and sport employment in the province.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship, Sport specialists, Economic factors, Socio-cultural factors, AHP

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